

backed planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) using the seedbox screening technique.

Seeds were sown in 40-cm rows, about 2-3 cm apart, in wooden trays (60 × 45 × 10 cm) in a greenhouse. TN1 was the susceptible check. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design, with five replications of

each wild species and variety. Seven days after sowing, seedlings were thinned to 15 per row and infested with 6-8 2d-instar WBPH nymphs per seedling. Plant damage was scored on a 0-9 scale at 7, 11, and 15 d after infestation (DAI).

The test entries exhibited resistance at 7 DAI. Mean damage ranged from 1 to 2.6, with TN1 rating 8.6 (see table). At

11 DAI, the wild rices rated 1, the cultivated varieties ranged from 2.2 to 6.2, and TN1, 9. At 15 DAI, the wild rices had maintained their extremely high level of resistance; the varieties exhibited moderately susceptible to susceptible reactions (see table). ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Xiang-zhong Xian No. 3: a high-yielding, widely useful rice variety in Hunan, China

Li Yong-Chao and Li Xiao-Xiang, Hunan Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Changsha, Hunan, China

Xiang-zhong Xian No. 3 is derived from the cross Xiang-zhao Xian No. 1///Ai-Bao//IR36/Shuang-Gui 36. It is a high-yielding, widely useful indica variety with multiple resistance. It was released in Jan 1992.

Xiang-zhong Xian No. 3 is resistant to whitebacked planthopper, brown planthopper, rice blast, and lodging. It responds well to high fertilizer levels.

Xiang-zhong Xian No. 3 performed well in monocropped midseason rice areas during 1990-91 regional trials in Hunan Province (see table). It also does well as a monocropped or dual-cropped, late-season variety. Average grain yield is 7.5 t/ha.

An additional advantage is its very good ratooning ability. The average ratoon crop had a 60-65 d growth duration and yield of 5.0 t/ha from 1989 to 1991 at the Agricultural Research Institute of Changde, Hunan Province. ■

La Plata Mochi F. A., a new rice variety from Argentina

A. A. Vidal, Estacion Experimental "Ing. Agr. Julio Hirschhorn," Facultad de Ciencias Agrarias y Forestales, Universidad Nacional de La Plata, Buenos Aires, Argentina

La Plata Mochi F. A. is the first Argentine waxy rice cultivar released from the rice program of the Faculty of Agrarian and Forestry Sciences of the National University of La Plata. It was developed to satisfy the demands of Koreans and Japanese in South America.

La Plata Mochi F. A. is 100 cm tall, resists lodging, and grows vigorously. It has a 125-d growth duration and yields about 5 t/ha. The panicle is 2.1-cm-long. Grain shattering is minimal and threshability intermediate.

The caryopsis is 5.7 cm long and 3.4 cm wide, with length-width ratio of 1.7. The waxy endosperm has 1.8% amylose content, gelatinization temperature of 6.0, alkali spreading value of 1.7, and 8.5% protein content. ■

Pant Dhan 10 replaces Pant Dhan 4 and Sarju 52 in western Uttar Pradesh, India

M. P. Pandey, S. C. Mani, H. Singh, J. P. Singh, S. Singh, and D. Singh, Plant Breeding Department, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, Uttar Pradesh (UP), India

Pant Dhan 10 (IR9763-11-2-2-3) was developed using the pedigree method following hybridization of IR32/Mahsuri/IR28 at IRRI, Philippines. It was evaluated as IET8616 in the All India Coordinated Trials.

It is a 92-cm semidwarf that matures in 125 d. It is suitable for transplanting in

the irrigated fields of Meerut, Agra, Moradabad, and Bareilly divisions and the tarai region of Nainital District of western UP.

Pant Dhan 10 outyielded Pant Dhan 4 by 11.2% and Sarju 52 by 8.6% in the 1988-91 Standard Varietal Trials (medium) at the Regional Agricultural Testing and Demonstration Centers at Meerut, Mathura, Bareilly, and Haldwani (Table 1).

Pant Dhan 10 showed moderately resistant reaction to bacterial blight and moderately resistant reaction to sheath blight and leaf blast across several locations. Pant Dhan 10 was field resistant to stem borer, leafroller, whorl

Performance of Xiang-zhong Xian No. 3 in 1990 and 1991 regional trials. Hunan, China.

	Xiang-zhong Xian No. 3		Shan You 63 (check)	
	1990	1991	1990	1991
Av grain yield (t/ha)	8.9	8.5	8.3	8.2
Highest grain yield (t/ha)	10.0	10.8	10.0	11.2
Growth duration (d)	128	130	138	139

Table 1. Mean performance of Pant Dhan 10 at 4 locations in western UP, India. 1988-91.

Year	Mean yield (t/ha)			% increase/decrease over	
	Pant Dhan 10	Pant Dhan 4 (check)	Sarju 52 (check)	Pant Dhan 4	Sarju 52
1988	5.3	4.1	4.8	+29.2	+10.4
1989	4.8	4.6	4.2	+4.3	+14.2
1990	3.9	4.1	3.7	-5.1	+5.4
1991	5.5	4.6	5.3	+19.5	+3.8
Mean	4.9	4.4	4.5	+11.6	+6.7